

The Effects of Speed on the Performance of Routing Protocols in Mobile Ad-hoc Networks

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Abstract—Mobile ad hoc network is a collection of mobile nodes communicating through wireless channels without any existing network infrastructure or centralized administration. Because of the limited transmission range of wireless network interfaces, multiple "hops" may be needed to exchange data across the network. Consequently, many routing algorithms have come into existence to satisfy the needs of communications in such networks. Researchers have conducted many simulations comparing the performance of these routing protocols under various conditions and constraints. One question that arises is whether speed of nodes affects the relative performance of routing protocols being studied. This paper addresses the question by simulating two routing protocols AODV and DSDV. Protocols were simulated using the ns-2 and were compared in terms of packet delivery fraction, normalized routing load and average delay, while varying number of nodes, and speed.

Keywords—AODV, DSDV, MANET, relative performance

I. INTRODUCTION

MOBILE ad hoc networks are formed by autonomous system of mobile nodes connected by wireless links without any preexisting communication infrastructure or centralized administration. Communication is directly between nodes or through intermediate nodes acting as routers. The advantages of such a network are rapid deployment, robustness, flexibility and inherent support for mobility. Ad hoc networks, due to their quick and economically less demanding deployment, find applications in military operations, collaborative and distributed computing, emergency operations, wireless mesh networks, wireless sensor networks and hybrid networks.

Due to node mobility, routes between two nodes may change. Therefore, it is not possible to establish fixed paths for delivery between networks. Because of this, routing is the most studied problem in mobile ad hoc networks and a

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number of routing protocols have been proposed [1-13], which are derived from either *distance-vector* [14] or *link-state* [15] based on classical routing algorithms.

Routing protocols for Mobile ad hoc networks can be classified into two main categories: Proactive or table driven routing protocols and Reactive or on-demand routing protocols. In proactive protocols, every node maintains the network topology information in the form of routing tables by periodically exchanging routing information. They include the Destination Sequenced Distance Vector (DSDV) [2], the Wireless Routing Protocol (WRP) [3], Source-Tree Adaptive Routing (STAR) [5] and Cluster-head Gateway Switch Routing protocol (CGSR) [4]. On the other hand, reactive protocols obtain routes only on demand, which include the Dynamic Source Routing (DSR) protocol [6], the Ad hoc On-demand Distance Vector (AODV) protocol [7], the Temporally Ordered Routing Algorithm (TORA) [8], and the Associativity Based Routing (ABR) protocol [10].

To determine the relative merits of the routing protocols, many papers comparing the performance of these protocols under various conditions and constraints [16-19] have been presented. However, until now no paper focusing on the effects of speed on the performance of routing protocols has been presented. It is the intent of this paper to compare the performance of routing protocols to determine whether the speed of nodes affects the relative performance of mobile ad hoc routing protocols.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II provides an overview of each of the routing protocols used in the study. The simulation environment and performance metrics are described in Section III and then the results are presented in Section IV. Finally Section V concludes the paper.

II. OVERVIEW OF ROUTING PROTOCOLS

As each protocol has its own merits and demerits, none of them can be claimed as absolutely better than others. To see how speed of mobile nodes affects their performance, two ad hoc routing protocols are selected for study – the Destination Sequenced Distance Vector (DSDV), the table-driven protocol and the Ad hoc On-Demand Distance Vector routing (AODV), an On-Demand protocol.

A. Destination-Sequenced Distance Vector (DSDV)

DSDV [2], an enhanced version of the distributed Bellman-Ford algorithm, belongs to the proactive or table driven family

where a correct route to any node in the network is always maintained and updated.

In DSDV, each node maintains a routing table that contains the shortest distance and the first node on the shortest path to every other node in the network. A sequence number created by the destination node tags each entry to prevent loops, to counter the count -to-infinity problem and for faster convergence. The tables are exchanged between neighbors at regular intervals to keep an up to date view of the network topology. The tables are also forwarded if a node finds a significant change in local topology. This exchange of table imposes a large overhead on the whole network. To reduce this potential traffic, routing updates are classified into two categories. The first is known as "full dump" which includes all available routing information. This type of updates should be used as infrequently as possible and only in the cases of complete topology change. In the cases of occasional movements, smaller "incremental" updates are sent carrying only information about changes since the last full dump. Each of these updates should fit in a single Network Protocol Data Unit (NPDU), and thus significantly decreasing the amount of traffic. Table updates are initiated by a destination with a new sequence number which is always greater than the previous one. Upon receiving an updated table a node either updates its tables based on the received information or holds it for some time to select the best metric received from multiple versions of the same update from different neighbors.

The availability of routes to all destinations at all times implies that much less delay is involved in the route setup process. The mechanism of incremental updates with sequence number tags makes the existing wired network protocols adaptable to mobile ad hoc networks. Hence, an existing wired network protocol can be applied to mobile ad hoc networks with fewer modifications. DSDV suffers from excessive control overhead that is proportional to the number of nodes in the network and therefore is not scalable in mobile ad hoc networks. Another disadvantage is stale routing information at nodes.

B. Ad Hoc On-Demand Distance Vector Routing (AODV)

AODV [7] is an improvement on the DSDV. AODV uses an on-demand approach for finding routes. Since it is an on-demand algorithm, a route is established only when it is required by a source node for transmitting data packets and it maintains these routes as long as they are needed by the sources.

AODV uses a destination sequence number, created by the destination, to determine an up to date path to the destination. A node updates its route information only if the destination sequence number of the current received packet is greater than the destination sequence number stored at the node. It indicates the freshness of the route accepted by the source. To prevent multiple broadcast of the same packet AODV uses broadcast identifier number that ensure loop freedom since the intermediate nodes only forward the first copy of the same packet and discard the duplicate copies.

To find a path to the destination, the source broadcasts a *Route Request* (RREQ) packet across the network. This RREQ contains the source identifier, the destination identifier, the source sequence number, the destination sequence number, the broadcast identifier and the time to live field. Nodes that receives RREQ either if they are the destination or if they have a fresh route to the destination, can respond to the RREQ by unicasting a *Route Reply* (RREP) back to the source node. Otherwise, the node rebroadcasts the RREQ.

When a node forwards a RREQ packet to its neighbors, it also records in its tables the node from which the first copy of the request came. This information is used to construct the reverse path for the RREP packet. AODV uses only symmetric links because the route reply packet follows the reverse path of route request packet. When a node receives a RREP packet, information about the previous node from which the packet was received is also stored in order to forward the data packets to this next node as the next hop toward the destination. Once the source node receives a RREP it can begin using the route to send data packets.

The source node rebroadcasts the RREQ if it does not receive a RREP before the timer expires. It attempts discovery up to some maximum number of attempts. If it does not discover a route after this maximum number of attempts, the session is aborted.

If the source moves then it can reinitiate route discovery to the destination. If one of the intermediate nodes move then the moved nodes neighbor realizes the link failure and sends a link failure notification to its upstream neighbors and so on till it reaches the source upon which the source can reinitiate route discovery if needed.

The main advantage of AODV is that routes are obtained on demand and destination sequence numbers are used to find the latest route to the destination. One of the disadvantages of AODV is that intermediate nodes can lead to inconsistent routes if the source sequence number is very old and the intermediate nodes have a higher but not the latest destination sequence number, thereby causing stale entries. Also multiple *Route Reply* (RREP) packets in response to a single *Route Request* (RREQ) packet can lead to heavy control overhead. Another is that periodic *hello* message leads to unnecessary bandwidth consumption.

Table 1 lists some of the basic differences between the two routing protocols.

TABLE I
 COMPARISON OF DSDV AND AODV ROUTING PROTOCOLS

Parameter	DSDV	AODV
Routing structure	Flat	Flat
Hello messages	Yes	Yes
Frequency of updates	Periodic and as needed	As required
Critical nodes	No	No
Loop-free	Yes	Yes
Multicasting capability	No	Yes
Routing metric	Shortest path	Freshest and shortest path
Utilizes sequence number	Yes	Yes
Time complexity	O (D)	O (2D)

Communication complexity	O (N)	O (2N)
Advantages	Small delays	Adaptable to highly dynamic topology
Disadvantages	Large overhead	Large delays

Abbreviations:

D = Diameter of the network

N = Number of nodes in the Network

III. SIMULATION AND PERFORMANCE METRICS

The simulations were performed using Network Simulator2 (NS-2) [20], particularly popular in the ad hoc networking community. The traffic sources are CBR (continuous bit – rate). The source-destination pairs are spread randomly over the network. The packet rate is 4 packets per second for 15 and 30 sources, 3 packets per sec for 45 sources. The data packet size is 512 bytes. The mobility model uses *random waypoint model* in a rectangular field of 500m x 500m with 50 nodes. In this mobility model, each node starts its journey from a random chosen location to a random chosen destination. Once the destination is reached, another random destination is chosen after a pause time. The speeds of nodes are varied between 0 to 25m/s. Different network scenario for different number of nodes and speeds are generated. Simulations are run for 100 seconds. The propagation model is the Two way ground model [21]. Simulation parameters are listed in table 2.

TABLE II
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Simulator	ns-2
Studied protocols	DSDV and AODV
Simulation time	100 seconds
Simulation area	500 m x 500 m
Transmission range	250 m
Node movement model	Random waypoint
Speed	0 – 25 m/s in steps of 5 m/s
Traffic type	CBR (UDP)
Data payload	512 bytes/packet
Packet rate	4 packets/sec for 15 and 30 sources 3 packets/sec for 45 sources
Node pause time	20s
Bandwidth	2 Mb/s

Performance Metrics

The following performance metrics are considered for evaluation:

Packet Delivery Fraction (PDF): The ratio of the data packets delivered to the destinations to those generated by the sources.

Average end-to-end delay: This includes all possible delays caused by buffering during route discovery latency, queuing at the interface queue, retransmission delays at the MAC, and propagation and transfer times.

Normalized routing load: The number of routing packets “transmitted” per data packet “delivered” at the destination.

Simulation metrics are listed in Table 3.

TABLE III

SIMULATION METRICS

ID	metrics	definition	formula	Example value
PS	packet sent	total number of packets sent by the source node	computed from trace file	2000
PR	Packet Received	Total number of packets received by the destination node	Computed from trace file	600
PDF	Packet Delivery Fraction	Ratio of packets received to packets sent	PDF = (PR/PS)*100%	88.5%
TD	Total Delivery Time	Time spent to deliver packets (PR)	Computed from trace file	1567.2
AD	Average end-to-end Delay	Delay spent to deliver each data packet	AD = TD/PR	6.235
RF	Routing Packets	Number of routing packets sent or forwarded	Computed from trace file	44
NRL	Normalized Routing Load	Number of routing packets per data packets	NRL = RF/PR	2.5

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation results are shown in the following section in the form of line graphs. Graphs show comparison between the two protocols by varying different numbers of sources on the basis of the above-mentioned metrics as a function of speed.

A. Packet Delivery Fraction (PDF)

Figure 1 shows a comparison between both the routing protocols on the basis of packet delivery fraction using a different number of traffic sources. As expected, Packet delivery fraction for AODV decreases as speed increases, since finding the route requires more and more routing traffic. Therefore less and less of the channel will be used for data transfer, thus decreasing the packet delivery.

(a)

(b)

(a)

(c)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 1 Packet delivery fraction vs. Speed for the 50-node model with (a) 15 sources, (b) 30 sources and (c) 45 sources.

Furthermore, as the number of nodes increases, more routing traffic will be generated (because AODV uses flooding for route discovery), which makes the packet delivery fraction decrease as the number of nodes increases.

For DSDV, as was the case with AODV, packet delivery fraction decreases as speed increases, since finding the route requires more and more routing traffic as speed increases thus making a lesser portion of the channel useful for data transfer.

Although the packet delivery fraction of both the protocols decreases as speed increases, but DSDV's packet delivery fraction decreases in a more steeper and more rapid fashion. This is due to excessive channel used by regular routing table updates. Furthermore, as mobility speed increases, more event-triggered updates are generated, resulting in even more packet delivery fraction decrease. This problem is not present in AODV since routes are only generated on-demand.

B. Average End to End Delay

Figure 2 show comparison between both the routing protocols on the basis of average end-to-end delay using different number of sources.

Fig. 2 Average End-to-End Delay vs. Speed for the 50-node model with (a) 15 sources, (b) 30 sources and (c) 45 sources.

AODV has less average end-to-end delay when compared to DSDV. This poor performance of DSDV is because of the reason that DSDV is not a On demand protocol and it keeps only one route per destination, therefore lack of alternate routes and presence of stale routes in the routing table when nodes are moving at higher rate leads to large delay.

C. Normalized Routing Load

Figure 3 show a comparison between both the routing protocols on the basis of normalized routing load using a different number of sources.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3 Normalized routing load vs. Speed for the 50-node model with (a) 15 sources, (b) 30 sources and (c) 45 sources.

In case of AODV the normalized routing load drastically increases as the number of nodes increases. The routing load also increases as the node mobility increases. As the number of nodes increases, more nodes will be flooding the network

with route request and consequently more nodes will be able to send route reply as well. As the node speed increases, a source node will have to generate more route requests to find a fresh enough route to destination node.

In case of DSDV the normalized routing load is almost the same with respect to node speed. The reason is that it is a table driven protocol, so a node does not need to find a route before transmitting packets.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper compared the two ad hoc routing protocols. AODV an On – Demand routing protocol, and DSDV a table driven protocol.

Simulation results show that packet delivery fraction of both the protocols decreases as speed increases, but DSDV's packet delivery fraction decreases in a steeper and more rapid fashion. AODV has less average end-to-end delay when compared to DSDV. The normalized routing load for AODV increases drastically as the number of nodes increases. The routing load also increases as the node mobility increases. But for DSDV the normalized routing load is almost the same with respect to node speed

REFERENCES

- [1] E. M. Royer and C. K. Toh, "A review of current routing protocols for ad hoc mobile wireless networks," *IEEE Personal Communications magazine*, April 1999, pp. 46–55.
- [2] C. E. Perkins and P. Bhagwat, "Highly Dynamic Destination-Sequenced Distance-Vector Routing (DSDV) for Mobile Computers," in *Proceedings of ACM SIGCOMM 1994*, August 1994, pp. 234-244.
- [3] S. Murthy and J. J. Garcia-Luna-Aceves, "An Efficient Routing Protocol for Wireless Networks," *ACM Mobile Networks and Applications Journal*, Special Issue on Routing in Mobile Communication Networks, Vol. 1, no. 2, October 1996, pp. 183-197.
- [4] C. C. Chiang, H. K. Wu, W. Liu and M. Gerla, "Routing in Clustered Multi-Hop Mobile Wireless Networks with Fading Channel," in *Proceedings of IEEE SICON 1997*, April 1997, pp. 197-211.
- [5] J. J. Garcia-Luna-Aceves and M. Spohn, "Source-Tree Routing in Wireless Networks," in *Proceedings of IEEE ICNP 1999*, October 1999, pp. 273-282.
- [6] D. B. Johnson and D. A. Malta, "Dynamic Source Routing in Ad Hoc Wireless Networks," *Mobile Computing*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, vol. 353, 1996, pp. 153-181.
- [7] C. E. Perkins and E. M. Royer, "Ad Hoc On-Demand Distance Vector Routing," *Proceedings of IEEE Workshop on Mobile Computing Systems and Applications 1999*, February 1999, pp. 90-100.
- [8] V. D. Park and M. S. Corson, "A Highly Adaptive Distributed Routing Algorithm for Mobile Wireless Networks," in *Proceedings of IEEE INFOCOM 1997*, April 1997, pp. 1405-1413.
- [9] Y. Ko and N. H. Vaidya, "Location-Aided Routing (LAR) in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks," in *Proceedings of ACM MOBICOM 1998*, October 1998, pp. 66-75.
- [10] C. K. Toh, "Associativity-Based Routing for Ad Hoc Mobile Networks," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 4, no. 2, March 1997, pp. 1-36.
- [11] P. Sinha, R. Shivkumar and V. Bharghavan, "CEDAR: A Core Extraction Distributed Ad Hoc Routing Algorithm," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 17, no. 8, August 1999, pp. 1454-1466.
- [12] Z. J. Haas, "The Routing Algorithm for the Reconfigurable Wireless Networks," in *Proceedings of ICUPC 1997*, vol. 2, October 1997, pp. 562-566.
- [13] R. S. Siodia, B. S. Manoj and C. Siva Ram Murthy, "A Preferred Link-Based Routing Protocol for Ad Hoc Wireless Networks," *Journal of Communications and Networks*, vol. 4, no. 1, march 2002, pp. 14-21.

- [14] Andrew S. Tanenbaum, Computer Networks. Fourth Edition, Prentice Hall, ch. 5, pp. 357-360.
- [15] Andrew S. Tanenbaum, Computer Networks. Fourth Edition, Prentice Hall, ch. 5, pp. 360-366.
- [16] J. Broch, D. A. Maltz, D. Johnson, Y. C. Hu and J. Jetcheva, "A Performance Comparison of Multi-Hop Wireless Ad Hoc Network Routing Protocols," in Proceedings of ACM/IEEE MOBICOM 1998, October 1998, pp. 85-97.
- [17] S. R. Das, C. E. Perkins and E. M. Royer, "Performance Comparison of Two On-Demand Routing Protocols for Ad Hoc Networks," in Proceedings of the IEEE INFOCOM 2000, March 2000, pp. 3-12.
- [18] P. Johansson, T. Larsson, N. Hedman, B. Mielczarek and M. Degermark, "Scenario-based Performance Analysis of Routing Protocols for Mobile Ad-hoc Networks," in Proceedings of the ACM/IEEE MOBICOM 1999, August 1999, pp.195-206.
- [19] S. R. Das, R. Cestaneda, J. Yan and R. Sengupta, "Comparative performance evaluation of routing protocols for mobile ad hoc networks," in proceedings of the IC3N 1998, October 1998, pp. 153-161.
- [20] K. Fall and K. Vardhan, The Network Simulator (ns-2). Available: <http://www.isi.edu/nsnam/ns>
- [21] T. S. Rappaport, Wireless Communications, Principles & Practices. Prentice Hall, 1996, ch. 3, pp. 70-74.

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